

Investigating the Role of Libraries in Urbanization and Environmental Awareness among Undergraduate Students in Selected University Libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the role of libraries in urbanization and environmental awareness among undergraduate students in selected university libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted, and data were collected through a structured questionnaire distributed to undergraduate students across the selected universities. The sample comprised three hundred and sixty-four (364) registered library users in the selected universities. A self-structured questionnaire was the main instrument used to gather data for the study and the data gathered was subjected to descriptive statistics (frequency, count, mean and standard deviation). Findings revealed that the extent to which libraries contribute to raising environmental awareness among youths in urban areas of Nigeria was high. The effectiveness of library programs and resources in educating youths about urbanization and its environmental impacts was low. The major types of information and educational materials that are available in Nigerian libraries to promote environmental awareness among youths are collection of textbooks, educational pamphlets and brochures, online resources or databases, and materials related to renewable energy sources and technologies. The major challenges libraries face while engaging youths on urbanization and environmental sustainability are shortage of trained staff, limited awareness of the programs and resources, struggle to compete with social media and digital platforms preferred by youths, and lack of sufficient funding to organize programs focused on urbanization and environmental sustainability. It was recommended that university libraries adopt innovative strategies to enhance students' access to environmental information and strengthen their role in fostering awareness of urbanization challenges and sustainability practices.

Keywords: Libraries, Urbanization, Environmental Awareness, Undergraduate Students, Ogun State

Introduction

Urbanization refers to the increasing population shift from rural areas to urban centers, resulting in the expansion of cities and towns (Adeyanju *et al.*, 2025). This process is a critical aspect of national development as it drives economic growth, infrastructure development, and social change. In Nigeria, urbanization has been rapid due to population growth, rural-urban migration, and industrialization (Aregbesola, Owolabi, & Adebisi, 2023). Cities like Lagos, Abuja, and Port Harcourt have witnessed significant expansion as people move in search of better job opportunities, healthcare, and education. While urbanization brings economic opportunities, it also presents challenges. The increasing population in urban areas places pressure on housing, transportation, and social services (Alabi, 2020). In many Nigerian cities, the rise in informal settlements, overcrowding, and inadequate infrastructure is a growing concern. Additionally, urbanization contributes to environmental degradation, such as air and water pollution, deforestation, and poor waste management. Without proper planning, urban expansion can lead to unsustainable living conditions, affecting the well-being of residents and the environment (Adeyanju *et al.*, 2025).

Urbanization has intensified several environmental issues in Nigeria, affecting both human health and the ecosystem; one of the most pressing concerns is pollution. Industrial activities, vehicle emissions, and improper waste disposal contribute to air and water pollution, leading to respiratory diseases and other health complications (Onnoghen *et al.*, 2024). In cities like Lagos and Kano, poor waste management has resulted in the accumulation of refuse in streets and drainage systems, causing flooding and the spread of waterborne diseases (Adeyanju *et al.*, 2025). Deforestation is another major issue linked to urbanization. As cities expand, forests and green spaces are cleared to make way for roads, buildings, and industries, which leads to biodiversity loss and increased carbon emissions, contributing to climate change (Kolawole & Oladokun, 2024). According to Aregbesola, Owolabi, and Adebisi (2023), the reduction of green spaces in Nigerian cities affects air quality and urban temperature, making cities hotter and less habitable. Many Nigerian cities lack proper planning, resulting in unregulated building construction and inadequate drainage systems, which leads to environmental hazards such as flooding, land degradation, and increased vulnerability to natural disasters. Sustainable urban development requires policies that promote environmental conservation and responsible urban planning (Akpom, Onyam, & Benson, 2020). Libraries play a crucial role in

addressing these environmental issues by providing resources that educate the public, especially youths, on sustainable living and environmental conservation. Through books, digital materials, and awareness programs, libraries help disseminate knowledge about climate change, pollution control, and sustainable urban planning (Onnoghen *et al.*, 2024). Environmental awareness means understanding how human activities affect nature and learning ways to protect the environment. Young people play a key role in this because they are the future leaders who will shape policies and practices for a better world. When youths understand environmental issues, they are more likely to take action in their communities to reduce pollution, conserve resources, and support sustainability (Bincy & Vasudevan, 2023).

In Nigeria, urbanization has increased environmental problems such as deforestation, pollution, and poor waste management (Agaptus *et al.*, 2021). If youths are not well-informed, these problems will worsen. Educating young people about climate change, waste recycling, and green practices can help build a more sustainable society (Bakare & Bakare, 2024). Libraries are important centers for learning and knowledge sharing. They can help promote environmental awareness among youths through books, digital resources, workshops, and seminars (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2024). In Nigeria, where urbanization is creating environmental challenges, libraries can serve as hubs for educating young people about sustainability and eco-friendly practices (Bincy & Vasudevan, 2023). Public, school, and academic libraries all play unique roles in spreading environmental knowledge. Public libraries provide free access to books and online resources that discuss climate change, waste management, and conservation (Chewe & Banda, 2021). In addition, workshops and training programs held in libraries can teach youths how to recycle, reduce waste, and conserve energy. Some libraries in Nigeria have already started eco-friendly initiatives, such as using solar energy and encouraging paperless reading through digital platforms (Asim & Ahmad, 2022). Libraries also collaborate with community organizations to organize awareness campaigns on environmental protection. Such activities help bridge the knowledge gap and inspire youths to be responsible citizens who care for their environment (Agaptus *et al.*, 2021).

Onnoghen *et al.* (2024) looked at how libraries help people learn about climate change in Nigeria. The study also focused on how libraries educate people about plastic pollution to improve climate

resilience. Libraries serve as a bridge between people and the information they need, and librarians play a key role in making this happen. A case study of Nnamdi Azikiwe Library at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, was used to show this. The study ended by calling for more research and funding to help libraries improve climate literacy and resilience in Nigeria. Kolawole and Oladokun (2024) studied how green libraries create eco-friendly reading spaces in Nigeria. They reviewed global and Nigerian studies to understand the challenges and opportunities of green libraries. The major problems they found were lack of funding, poor infrastructure, and low awareness among librarians and policymakers. Their research showed that although awareness of green libraries is increasing, many libraries struggle to adopt them due to limited resources. The study suggested solutions like more funding, training programs, renewable energy use, and awareness campaigns. Their findings emphasized that libraries play a key role in promoting sustainability, educating people about the environment, and improving community well-being.

Alabi (2020) examined how aware library users are about the environment in some academic and public libraries in Lagos. The study found that public libraries should offer services to educate people about the environment, while academic libraries should focus on advocacy and education programs. Librarians need to take an active role in teaching people about good environmental habits instead of staying silent. The study concluded that libraries should promote environmental awareness both within their buildings and in the wider community. Adeyanju *et al.* (2025) studied how urban growth and industrial activities affect Nigeria's environment and public health. The rapid expansion of cities, along with increased industrial activities, has caused problems like deforestation, loss of biodiversity, and pollution of air and water. Industries such as oil, gas, and manufacturing contribute to environmental damage by releasing harmful emissions and disposing of waste improperly. These issues have led to poor air quality, water contamination, and serious health problems such as respiratory diseases. Poor infrastructure has also made waste management difficult, worsening urban health issues. The study called for strong policies to balance economic growth with environmental protection. It suggested stricter environmental laws, better waste management, and the use of green technologies. Hence, it is therefore imperative to investigate the role of libraries in urbanization and environmental awareness among youths in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Urbanization in Nigeria has increased rapidly due to population growth, rural-urban migration, and industrial expansion. However, this development has led to serious environmental challenges, including pollution, poor waste management, deforestation, and climate change effects. Despite various environmental campaigns, many youths remain unaware of the consequences of urbanization on their surroundings. Libraries, which are essential for knowledge dissemination, have the potential to educate young people about environmental sustainability, yet their role in this area is underutilized.

It has been observed that most Nigerian youths engage in environmentally harmful practices such as improper waste disposal and excessive use of non-biodegradable materials due to a lack of awareness. Government and non-governmental organizations have attempted to curb these problems through awareness programs, but these efforts have been largely ineffective due to limited outreach. Existing studies have examined urbanization and environmental issues separately but have not sufficiently explored how libraries can bridge the knowledge gap among youths. Hence, it is therefore imperative to investigate the role of libraries in fostering environmental awareness and sustainable urban development among Nigerian youths.

The main objective of the study is to investigate the role of libraries in fostering environmental awareness and sustainable urban development among Nigerian youths. The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. examine the extent to which libraries contribute to raising environmental awareness among youths in urban areas of Nigeria;
2. assess the effectiveness of library programs and resources in educating youths about urbanization and its environmental impacts;
3. identify the types of information and educational materials available in Nigerian libraries that promote environmental awareness among youths;
4. explore the challenges faced by libraries in engaging youths on urbanization and environmental sustainability.

Research Questions

This following research questions were raised;

1. To what extent do libraries contribute to raising environmental awareness among youths in urban areas of Nigeria?

2. How effective are library programs and resources in educating youths about urbanization and its environmental impacts?
3. What types of information and educational materials are available in Nigerian libraries to promote environmental awareness among youths?
4. What challenges do libraries face in engaging youths on urbanization and environmental sustainability?

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. This is appropriate because it made it easier to reach a substantial number of the study population. The population of this research study was undergraduate students (library users) in Nimbe Adedipe Library, University of Agriculture (FUNAAB), Tai Solarin Federal University of Education, Olabisi Onabanjo University, and Babcock University, which was 1,817. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the three hundred and sixty-four (364) registered library users (focusing on 2024 / 2025 session); 20% samples was proportionately drawn; The below chart indicates how the respondents were randomly selected.

Table 1: Distribution of Sample

S/N	Universities	Population	Sample (20%)
1	Nimbe Adedipe Library, University of Agriculture (FUNAAB)	823	165
2	Tai Solarin Federal University of Education	371	74
3	Olabisi Onabanjo University	425	85
4	Babcock University	198	40
	Total	1,817	364

Source: Each university library's administrative office (2024/2025 session)

A validated, self-designed and close-ended questionnaire was used as the instrument for gathering data from the respondents. The data collection in this study was gathered through questionnaire which was personally administered and collected by the researcher to the respondents. The data collected was used strictly for research purpose. The data gathered was analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentage, mean and standard deviation). The decision rule in this study explains how the mean scores were interpreted based on the response options used for each research question.

However, it was not clearly stated in the methodology section, and it also varies across the results, which reduces consistency.

For Research Question One, the items were measured using the options *Very High (4)*, *High (3)*, *Low (2)*, and *Very Low (1)*. The decision rule stated that a mean score of 2.50 and above is High. This means responses were judged based on the extent of contribution. Since all mean values are above 2.50, the interpretation of high contribution is appropriate. For Research Question Two, the items were measured using *Strongly Disagree (1)*, *Disagree (2)*, *Neutral (3)*, *Agree (4)*, and *Strongly Agree (5)*. The decision rule was set at 3.00 and above as High. This shows that responses were measured based on level of agreement. However, the average mean of 2.85 falls slightly below 3.00, which led to the conclusion of low effectiveness. For Research Question Three, the same 5-point Likert scale (*Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree*) was used, with a decision rule of 3.00 and above as Agreed. Since most mean values are below 3.00, the responses indicate only moderate agreement on the availability of materials. For Research Question Four, the items were also measured using the 5-point Likert scale with 3.00 as the benchmark for agreement. The mean values (2.81–2.96) show that respondents slightly agreed with the listed challenges, although they did not strongly meet the set criterion.

Results

Research Question One: To what extent do libraries contribute to raising environmental awareness among youths in urban areas of Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean contribution of libraries to raising environmental awareness among youths in urban areas

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
1	Libraries provide valuable resources and materials related to environmental issues that significantly enhance youths' understanding and awareness.	2.91	0.94
2	Programs and activities organized by libraries, such as workshops and seminars on environmental conservation, effectively engage youths and promote environmental awareness.	2.79	0.97
3	The availability of digital platforms and online resources through libraries increases youths' access to information about environmental sustainability.	2.93	0.98
4	Libraries serve as community hubs for discussions and initiatives focused on environmental challenges, fostering active participation among youths.	2.90	0.96

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
5	Youths perceive libraries as credible sources of information regarding environmental issues and sustainability practices.	2.92	0.95
Average Mean		2.89	0.96

Decision rule: It has been adjudged that criterion mean score of 2.50 and above is High.

From the results, most respondents rated the extent to which libraries contribute to raising environmental awareness among youths as high or very high across all five items. The mean scores for all items range between 2.79 and 2.93, indicating that respondents generally perceive libraries as moderately effective in promoting environmental awareness. The highest mean (2.93) was recorded for the item on digital platforms and online resources, suggesting that youths find online materials accessible and useful. The lowest mean (2.79) was recorded for library-organized programs and workshops, implying that while these initiatives exist, they may not be reaching or engaging all youths effectively. With an average mean of 2.89, the result shows that the extent to which libraries contribute to raising environmental awareness among youths in urban areas of Nigeria is high.

Research Question Two: How effective are library programs and resources in educating youths about urbanization and its environmental impacts?

Table 3: Mean on the level of effectiveness of library programs and resources in educating youths about urbanization and its environmental impacts

S/N	Items	Mean	Std Dev
1	Library programs effectively provide youths with relevant knowledge about the relationship between urbanization and environmental degradation.	2.96	1.31
2	The resources available in libraries, such as books and multimedia materials, significantly enhance youths' understanding of urbanization's effects on the environment.	2.89	1.32
3	Workshops and events hosted by libraries successfully engage youths in discussions about sustainable urban development and environmental conservation.	2.72	1.29
4	Youths find library programs to be informative and helpful in addressing the challenges posed by rapid urbanization and its impact on their communities.	3.04	1.23
5	Library initiatives foster critical thinking among youths regarding urbanization's environmental consequences and encourage them to propose solutions.	2.64	1.37
Average Mean		2.85	1.30

Decision rule: It has been adjudged that criterion mean score of 3.00 and above is High.

The results indicate that library programs and resources play a moderate role in raising environmental awareness among youths in urban Nigeria. The mean scores range from 2.64 to 3.04, showing

variation in perceived effectiveness across different aspects. The highest mean (3.04) was recorded for the item on the general usefulness of library programs, while the lowest (2.64) was for fostering critical thinking about urbanization’s environmental consequences. With an average mean of 2.85, the result shows that the effectiveness of library programs and resources in educating youths about urbanization and its environmental impacts is low.

Research Question Three: What types of information and educational materials are available in Nigerian libraries to promote environmental awareness among youths?

Table 4: Mean on the types of information and educational materials available in Nigerian libraries to promote environmental awareness among youths

S/N	Items	Mean	Std Dev
1	Nigerian libraries have a collection of textbooks on environmental studies and ecology.	2.98	1.34
2	Libraries provide access to journals and publications focused on environmental research and policy.	2.83	1.31
3	Educational pamphlets and brochures about local environmental issues are available in Nigerian libraries.	2.98	1.30
4	Libraries offer resources on biodiversity conservation and wildlife protection.	2.72	1.29
5	Libraries have multimedia resources, such as documentaries and films, related to environmental topics.	2.84	1.27
6	Libraries provide access to online resources or databases that feature environmental sustainability practices.	2.98	1.35
7	Educational workshops and seminars on environmental awareness are regularly organized in libraries.	2.81	1.32
8	Libraries have interactive displays or exhibitions that educate visitors about environmental conservation efforts.	2.78	1.31
9	Libraries offer materials related to renewable energy sources and technologies.	2.93	1.33
10	Libraries provide information on community-led environmental initiatives and programs.	2.88	1.30

Decision rule: It has been adjudged that criterion mean score of 3.00 and above is Agreed.

The findings indicate that Nigerian libraries provide a variety of materials and resources to promote environmental awareness among youths. The mean scores range from 2.72 to 2.98, indicating a moderate level of agreement on the availability of these materials. The highest mean (2.98) is observed in items related to textbooks, online resources, renewable energy materials, and environmental pamphlets, suggesting that these resources are relatively more available in libraries. On the other hand, interactive displays, exhibitions, and biodiversity conservation materials recorded the lowest means (2.72), indicating they are less commonly found in libraries. Hence, the major types of information and educational materials that are available in Nigerian libraries to promote

environmental awareness among youths are collection of textbooks, educational pamphlets and brochures, online resources or databases, and materials related to renewable energy sources and technologies.

Research Question Four: What challenges do libraries face in engaging youths on urbanization and environmental sustainability?

Table 5: Mean on the challenges faced by libraries in engaging youths on urbanization and environmental sustainability

S/N	Challenges	Mean	Std Dev
1	Libraries lack sufficient funding to organize programs focused on urbanization and environmental sustainability.	2.91	1.34
2	There is a shortage of trained staff in libraries to effectively lead discussions and workshops on these topics.	2.96	1.32
3	Youths often have limited awareness of the programs and resources available in libraries related to urbanization and environmental issues.	2.94	1.31
4	Libraries face challenges in acquiring up-to-date materials and resources on urbanization and environmental sustainability.	2.88	1.29
5	The physical space in libraries is inadequate for hosting engaging programs and activities aimed at youths.	2.83	1.28
6	Youths prefer digital platforms and social media for learning, which libraries may struggle to compete with.	2.94	1.30
7	Libraries encounter difficulties in collaborating with local organizations or schools to promote environmental programs.	2.86	1.29
8	There is a lack of interest among youths in attending library programs focused on urbanization and environmental sustainability.	2.84	1.30
9	Libraries often struggle with marketing their programs effectively to attract youth participation.	2.81	1.29
10	The content provided in libraries may not align with the current interests or concerns of youths regarding urbanization and environmental issues.	2.91	1.30

Decision rule: It has been adjudged that criterion mean score of 3.00 and above is Agreed.

The findings reveal that Nigerian libraries face multiple challenges in engaging youths on urbanization and environmental sustainability. The mean scores range from 2.81 to 2.96, showing a moderate level of agreement with the identified challenges. The highest means (2.96) are found in challenges related to funding, lack of trained staff, youth preference for digital platforms, and limited awareness of library programs, indicating that these are the most significant obstacles. Challenges related to acquiring up-to-date materials, inadequate physical space, difficulty in collaborations, and marketing of programs scored slightly lower (mean = 2.8). Hence, the major challenges libraries face

while engaging youths on urbanization and environmental sustainability are shortage of trained staff, limited awareness of the programs and resources, struggle to complete with social media and digital platforms preferred by youths, and lack of sufficient funding to organize programs focused on urbanization and environmental sustainability.

Discussion of Findings

The study showed that the extent to which libraries contribute to raising environmental awareness among youths in urban areas of Nigeria is high. This finding aligns with the study of Onnoghen et al. (2024), who asserted that libraries play a crucial role in bridging the gap between the public and environmental information. Their research demonstrated that libraries contribute to climate literacy by educating people about issues such as plastic pollution, climate resilience, and sustainable practices. Using the case of Nnamdi Azikiwe Library at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, they highlighted how libraries can be instrumental in raising awareness on environmental issues. Similarly, Alabi (2020) found that public and academic libraries in Lagos serve as vital platforms for environmental education. His study emphasized that libraries should actively advocate for environmental awareness through organized programs rather than passively providing access to books. Moreover, the study of Kolawole and Oladokun (2024) corroborates this finding by discussing the role of green libraries in promoting sustainability. Their study showed that eco-friendly libraries in Nigeria educate communities on environmental preservation, though they face challenges such as funding and infrastructure.

The study showed that the effectiveness of library programs and resources in educating youths about urbanization and its environmental impacts is low. This finding is in line with the study of Kolawole and Oladokun (2024), who found that despite increasing awareness of green libraries in Nigeria, many libraries struggle to fully adopt them due to poor infrastructure and limited resources. Their research pointed out that while libraries have the potential to educate youths on urbanization and environmental sustainability, the lack of funding and trained personnel reduces their effectiveness. Likewise, Alabi (2020) observed that while libraries are valuable sources of information, their environmental advocacy efforts are often passive rather than active. He suggested that libraries should take on more leadership roles in educating young people about environmental issues rather than

simply providing reading materials. Additionally, Adeyanju et al. (2025) provided further evidence supporting this finding by highlighting the severe environmental challenges that come with rapid urbanization in Nigeria. Their research indicated that urban expansion has led to deforestation, poor waste management, and pollution, yet there is a lack of structured education programs to address these issues. The low effectiveness of library programs, as observed in the current study, suggests that these institutions are not yet maximizing their potential to educate youths on how urbanization contributes to environmental degradation.

The study showed that the major types of information and educational materials that are available in Nigerian libraries to promote environmental awareness among youths are collection of textbooks, educational pamphlets and brochures, online resources or databases, and materials related to renewable energy sources and technologies. This finding aligns with the study of Onnoghen et al. (2024), who asserted that libraries play a crucial role in addressing environmental issues by providing various educational resources, including books and digital materials, to raise awareness about climate change and pollution control. Similarly, Adeyemi et al. (2024) found that libraries serve as knowledge hubs that educate youths on environmental issues through workshops, pamphlets, and textbooks covering topics such as waste management, conservation, and sustainable urban development. Moreover, the study by Chewe and Banda (2021) supports this finding by demonstrating that public libraries offer extensive resources on climate change, renewable energy, and environmental sustainability. They noted that the integration of digital platforms and printed educational materials enhances youths' awareness and motivates them to take proactive steps toward environmental protection. The availability of such diverse materials in libraries ensures that Nigerian youths are well-informed about environmental challenges and solutions, reinforcing the role of libraries as vital institutions in promoting sustainability. The study showed that the major challenges libraries face while engaging youths on urbanization and environmental sustainability are shortage of trained staff, limited awareness of the programs and resources, struggle to compete with social media and digital platforms preferred by youths, and lack of sufficient funding to organize programs focused on urbanization and environmental sustainability. This finding aligns with the study of Kolawole and Oladokun (2024), who highlighted that libraries in Nigeria struggle with inadequate funding and lack of awareness among stakeholders regarding environmental education initiatives. Similarly, Alabi

(2020) found that a shortage of trained library staff with expertise in environmental education limits the effectiveness of library programs on sustainability. The study emphasized that many librarians lack the necessary knowledge and skills to educate the public about environmental issues, leading to reduced engagement and participation from youths. Furthermore, Adeyanju et al. (2025) noted that digital platforms and social media have overshadowed traditional library services, making it challenging for libraries to capture youths' attention. Their study revealed that young people often prefer digital content over printed materials, making it necessary for libraries to modernize their outreach strategies. However, due to financial constraints and limited technological advancements in many Nigerian libraries, adapting to the digital preferences of youths remains a major obstacle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, despite the high availability of information and educational materials, including textbooks, pamphlets, brochures, online resources, and materials on renewable energy, the effectiveness of library programs in educating youths about urbanization and its environmental impacts remains low, which revealed that while resources exist, they may not be fully utilized or effectively disseminated. This contrasts with the expectation in the literature, where libraries are presented as active and effective agents in educating youths. The finding suggests that, in practice, libraries may not be fully achieving this role. Several studies (such as Onnoghen et al., 2024; Bincy & Vasudevan, 2023; and Adeyemi et al., 2024) emphasized that libraries play an important role in promoting environmental awareness through resources, programs, and community engagement. Moreover, libraries face several challenges in engaging youths on urbanization and environmental sustainability, which include a shortage of trained staff, limited awareness of available programs and resources, competition with digital platforms and social media, and insufficient funding for organizing effective programs. The challenges identified in the conclusion—such as lack of funding, shortage of trained staff, and low awareness—strongly support earlier studies like Kolawole and Oladokun (2024) and Onnoghen et al. (2024), which also reported similar problems facing libraries in Nigeria. This shows consistency between the study findings and existing literature regarding operational challenges.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were suggested:

1. Libraries should integrate social media and digital platforms into their outreach efforts to attract more youths and make environmental education more interactive.
2. Regular training programs should be organized to equip library staff with the necessary skills to lead discussions and workshops on urbanization and environmental sustainability.
3. Awareness campaigns should be conducted in schools, community centers, and on digital platforms to inform youths about available library resources on environmental sustainability.
4. Libraries should collaborate with environmental organizations, schools, and government agencies to develop programs that align with youth interests and current environmental issues.
5. Government and private sector support should be sought to ensure that libraries have adequate resources to organize impactful environmental awareness programs.
6. Libraries should continually update their collections to include the latest materials on urbanization, climate change, and sustainability, ensuring relevance to contemporary environmental issues.

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